

THE IMPACT OF EXCHANGE RATE VOLATILITY ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA

GODWIN MFON EKPO

Department of Economics, Ritman University, Ikot Ekpene, Akwa Ibom,
Nigeria,

Email: goddymfon@yahoo.com Phone: +234-803-8722-584

EFFIWAT B. IWATT PHD

University of Uyo, Uyo, Akwa Ibom, Nigeria

E-mail: effiwattbiwatt@uniyo.edu.ng +234-806-2629-872

&

ANTHONY AKWAWA UDUIMOH PhD

Department of Banking and Finance, Ritman University, Ikot Ekpene, Akwa
Ibom, Nigeria

Email: auakwawa57@gmail.com Phone: +234-814-8974-571

Abstract

This study examines the impact of exchange rate volatility on economic growth in Nigeria using time series data from 1970-2020. Multiple regression and co-integration methods are employed to analyze the data. The objectives of this study are; to examine the causal relationship between exchange rate volatility and economic growth in Nigeria from 1970-2020; to investigate the impact of exchange rate volatility on trade balance in Nigeria from 1970-2020. Being a time series data to avoid spurious regression results, the first step is to test for the stationarity of the data using the Philip Peron and Augmented Dickey Fuller Unit root test. All the variables were stationary at 1(1). The pair-wise Granger causality test was used to investigate the causal relationship between exchange rate volatility and economic growth. Major findings from the study are as follows: that there is no causal relationship between exchange rate volatility and economic growth in Nigeria. Exchange rate volatility (EXCH) recorded both positive and negative impact on economic growth (GDPR) although; the rate of negative impacts outweighs that of the positive impact. Trade balance (BOP) has an insignificant positive effect on gross domestic product (GDPR). Based on these findings, the study recommends that the Nigerian Government should pay serious attention to factors that stimulate exchange rate fluctuations like high inflation and budget deficit and encourage an export led economy, avoid systematic currency devaluations in order to maintain exchange rate volatility at a rate that allows adjustment of the balance of payments amongst other recommendations.

Keywords: Exchange rate, Volatility, Economic growth, Cointegration, Trade Balance

1. INTRODUCTION

Exchange rate volatility is an important factor which investors take into consideration in their investment decision (Unugbro, 2007). As such, the mobility of goods and services across national frontier in a direction involves the movement of foreign exchange in the opposite direction, hence creating the need for a rate of exchange between the currencies of two trading partners to settle indebtedness arising from trade involving them (Nzotta, 2004). Tracing back to 1960, when Nigeria became politically independent, it can be said that exchange rate management was used to influence Nigeria's macro-economic performance. Exchange rate is one of the most important policy variables which determines the trade flows, foreign direct investment, inflation, international reserve and steady economic growth. Due to misapplication and bad choice of exchange rate regime, many African countries faced crisis in 1990's.

However, there is no consensus in the theoretical or empirical literature about any unique effect of the exchange rate volatility on macroeconomic indicators. The role of exchange rate is very significant because it directly and indirectly affects the domestic price level, profitability of traded goods and services, allocation of resources and investment decisions. Theoretically, one may argue that exchange rate as a volatile subject matter is an important factor that affects economic performance due to its impact on macroeconomic variables like output, import and export prices, interest rate and inflation rate. In a bid to attain high economic performance (growth) that will lead to rapid economic development and reduction of poverty, the Nigerian government has formulated various exchange rate policies; from the fixed parity between the Nigeria Naira and the British Pound (1960-1967), fixed parity between the naira and the American Dollar (1967-1974), Independent exchange rate policy (1974-1976), pegging the Naira to an import-weighted basket of currencies (1976-1985) and the market determined exchange rate policy (1986-Date). According to Obansa, Okoroafor, Aluko and Millicent (2013), exchange rate determines the participation of external sector in cross-border trade. By reducing unemployment level, price stability and increase in standard of living, exchange rate can be seen as one of the most important and very useful macroeconomic variables that a country uses to achieve its macroeconomic objectives.

When the productive capacity of a country improves, growth is perceived to have taken place (Akpan, 2008). Actual production of goods and services stimulates exports and sometimes requires the importation of raw materials which involves transactions in foreign currencies, (Oyovwi, 2012). Showing the implications of Nigeria's over-dependence on export of oil, (Jin, 2008), said that the economy is highly prone to external shocks because where there is a major fall in oil price, foreign exchange rate earnings will decline noticeably and there will be destabilizing effects on exchange rate as there will be less than enough stock of foreign currencies to defend the local currency at the foreign exchange market. This major shift in exchange rate would result in a near equal adjustment in the allocation of a country's

local resources and possibly move the economic structure away from the production of exportable commodities to the services sector. In Nigeria, exchange rate has changed from regulated to deregulated regimes. It was agreed that the exchange rate of the naira was relatively stable between 1973 and 1979 during the oil boom year and when the agricultural products accounted for more than 70% of the nation's gross domestic product (GDP). After adopting the structural Adjustment Policy in 1986, the country moved from a pegged regime to a flexible exchange regime where exchange rate is left completely to be determined by the market forces but rather, the prevailing system is the manage float whereby monetary authorities intervene periodically in the foreign exchange market in order to attain some strategic objectives (Mordi, 2006).

It is the goal of every economy to have a stable rate of exchange with its trading partners. In Nigeria, this goal was never reached in spite of the fact the country embarked on devaluation to promote export as a result, stabilizing the rate of exchange. The government went further to establish the foreign exchange market (FEM) to stabilize the exchange rate depending on the state of balance of payments, the rate of inflation, domestic liquidity and employment. Failure to realize this goal subjected the Nigerian economy to the challenge of a constantly fluctuating exchange rate till date. The exchange rate of the naira was relatively stable between 1975 and 1979 during the oil boom. This was also the situation prior to 1990 when agricultural products accounted for more than 70% of the nation's gross domestic product (GDP) (Ewa, 2011). However, as a result of the development in the petroleum sector in the 1970s, the share of agriculture in total exports declined significantly while that of oil increased. From 1981, the World Oil Market started to deteriorate and thus economic crisis emerged in Nigeria because of the country's over dependence on oil revenue.

To underscore the importance of oil export to Nigerian economy, the gross national product (GNP) fell from \$76 billion in 1986 to \$40 billion in 1996 and a good number of growth variables became negative as a result of the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP). Some of the measures the government adopted to help reduce the incessant depreciation of the naira was the introduction of the Inter-bank Foreign Exchange Market (IFEM) in 1999, the Autonomous Foreign Exchange Market (AFEM) and the re-introduction of the Dutch Auction System (DAS) in July 2002, with the objectives of realigning the exchange rate of the naira, conserving external reserving, enhancing market transparency and curbing capital flight in the country. Other measures adopted included the unfettered grant access holders of ordinary accounts to their funds, while utilization of funds in the non-oil export domiciliary accounts were permitted for eligible transactions. In spite of all these measures, the value of naira has continued to depreciate. Hence inhibiting the economy from experiencing desirable growth. In the light of the above, this work attempts to investigate the nexus between exchange rate volatility and economic growth in Nigeria.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: The next section discusses the review of conceptual framework, theoretical and empirical evidences. Section 3 discusses the methodology. Results and interpretations are presented just before the summary and conclusions.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Framework

2.1.1 Exchange Rate and Exchange Rate Regime in Nigeria

Exchange rate can be defined in varying contexts but the underlying element, is that it is the price of one currency in terms of another, especially in relation to trading partner's economies. Exchange rates can either be fixed or floating. Fixed exchange rates are decided by the central banks of a country whereas floating exchange rate decided by the mechanism of market demand and supply. Exchange rate arrangements are broadly classified into three: namely, fixed or pegged arrangements, flexible arrangements and in-between category of arrangements, flexible arrangement and in-between category of arrangements with "limited flexibility". Each variety or alternative has different implications which determines the extent to which countries participate in foreign exchange markets. When a monetary authority decides to fix exchange rate against other currencies, they make a commitment to intervene in the market, buying and selling their currency whenever necessary to keep the exchange rate from changing. In practice, by controlling the extent to which, and conditions under which, they intervene in exchange markets. Peter (1997), states that countries may attempt to manage their exchange rates which essentially any degree of flexibility they desire. Jhingan (2011) stated that the crucial component of macroeconomic policy in a country is the choice of an appropriate exchange policy. Obadan (2006) stated that exchange rate is one of the most important macroeconomic variable necessary for the conduct of general economic policy making. Apart from connecting the price systems in different countries and enabling businessmen to compare prices directly, they are important in promoting exports and discouraging imports, thereby achieving health balance of payments position.

2.1.2 Volatility

Volatility measures the rate and magnitude of price changes around a trend. In other words, it captures the deviation of the actual observed price from its normal or expected value (Pindyck, 2002) the computation and estimation of price volatility is not unique to exchange rate and is heavily discussed in a wide range of economic fields. Earlier studies on volatility focused on asset or security returns. In principle, measures of exchange rate. Volatility can be classified into two broad categories (Matthews, 2010). First, realized historical volatility that measures that volatility of observed past prices. Secondly, stochastic volatility which captures volatility at a given point in time also considering past realization of volatility. From the foregoing, volatility in this context could rightly be defined as the rate at which the price of exchange rate increases or decreases for a given period (Kashhif, A. Slade, M.E.,

Blaze, K. 2010). It is measured by calculating the standard deviation of the annualized returns over a given period of time. In financial market, volatility measurement is based on the standard deviation of the asset return, a variable that appears in option pricing formulas, where it denotes the volatility of the underlying asset return from now to the expiration of the option (Shiller and Radikoko, 2014).

2.1.3 Economic Growth

Economic growth of a nation's real gross national product (UNP) tells us how rapidly the economy's total real output of goods and services is increasing. Hence, economic growth refers to the continuous increase in a country's national income or the total volume of goods and services. A very good indicator of economic growth is the increase in Gross National Product (GNP) over a long period of time. Economic Growth is measured by increase in output of goods and services overtime and as stated by Akpan (2008), economic growth is said to occur when a country's productive capacity is on the increase.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 The Mint Parity Theory

The earliest theory of foreign exchange has been the mint parity theory. This theory was applicable for those countries which had the same metallic standard (gold or silver). Under the gold standard, countries had their standard currency unit either of gold or it was freely convertible into gold of a given purity. The value of currency unit under standard was defined in terms of weight of gold of a specified purity contained in it. The central bank of the country was always willing to buy and sell gold up to an unlimited extent at the given price. The price at which the standard currency unit of the country was convertible into gold was called the mint price. Suppose the official price of gold in Britain was £20 per ounce and in the United States it was \$80 per ounce, these were the mint prices of gold in the two countries. The rate of exchange between these two currencies would be determined as £20=\$80 or £1=\$4.

This rate of exchange determined on weight-to-weight basis of the metallic contents of currencies of the two countries was called mint par of exchange between them. Under the gold standard, the balance of payments adjustments were made through the five international flows of gold. The export and import of gold involved costs of packing, freight, insurance, interest etc. consequently, the actual rate of exchange between two currencies could vary above and below the mint parity by the extent of cost of gold export.

2.2.2 The Purchasing Power Parity Theory:

The Purchasing Power Parity Theory enunciates the determination of the rate of exchange between two inconvertible paper currencies. Although this theory can be traced back to Wheatley and Ricardo, yet the credit for developing it in a systematic way has gone to the Swedish economist Gustav Cassel. The theory states that the equilibrium rate of exchange is determined by the equality of the purchasing power of two inconvertible paper currencies. It implies that the rate of exchange between

two inconvertible paper currencies is determined by the internal price levels in two countries.

According to Jhingan (2011), the equality of the relative change in the price levels in two countries determines the equilibrium exchange rate between the two inconvertible paper currencies. International competitiveness is measured by comparing the relative prices of the good from different countries when these are measured in a common currency. The purchasing power parity path for the nominal exchange rate is the path that would keep competitiveness constant overtime. According to this theory, countries with higher domestic inflation that their competitors would face a depreciating nominal exchange rate while countries with lower domestic inflation that their competitors would face appreciating exchange rates. The earlier and leading theoretical foundation for the choices of exchange rate regimes rests on the optimal currency area (OAC) theory, developed by Mundell (1961) and Mckinnon (1963). This literature focuses on trade and stabilization of the business cycle. According to the theory, a fixed exchange rate regime can increase trade and output growth by reducing exchange rate uncertainty and thus the cost of hedging and also encourage investment by lowering currency premium from interest rates. Later theories focused on financial market stabilization of speculated financial behavior to emerging economics.

According to the theory, a fixed regime can increase trade and output growth by providing a nominal anchor and often needed credibility for monetary policy by avoiding complete depreciation, and enhancing the development of financial markets, (Barro and Gordon, (1983), Calvo and Vegh (2004), Edwards and Savastano (2000) Eichengreen *et al.* (1999) and Frankle (2003) among others. The theory also suggests that affixed regime can only delay the necessary relative price adjustments and often lead to speculative attacks therefore, many developing countries suffer from a fear of floating, large comparatively closed economies such as Japan, are sensitive to large exchange swings, in particular, the case of application.

2.2.3 The Neoclassical Growth Model

The Solow and Swan (1956) model of economic growth, which commonly represent the Neo-classical model are based on aggregate production function such as Cobb-Douglas and a capital accumulation equation. These models predict that the level of per capita income is determined by the population growth rate and the rate of investment and also does not account for technological progress. Economic growth can take place temporarily and last only until capita income reaches, its steady state level. As an exogenous variable, technology is incorporated in the second model introduced by Solow in 1956. The major significance of the neoclassical growth model is that the level of per capita output is determined by technological progress, investment rate and population growth rate. While sustained growth rate of per capita output overtime is determined by technological changes, other temporary shocks such as policy changes affect growth temporarily until a new steady state level is attained. In this model, if there is no technological progress, steady state per capita

output does not grow and it is dependent on exogenous factors. Although, because of diminishing returns to capital, per capita output in the long run grows at the rate of exogenously given technological progress. Although economic policies can affect the level of output (growth rate), when the economy is in transition from one steady state to another, they don't affect the steady state economic growth. In the steady state of the neo-classical model, all growths are due to technological progress. The model is criticized on the grounds that technological progress is taken as an exogenous factor and without it, the model assumes there is no economic growth.

2.2.4 Endogenous Growth Model

From the weakness of the Neoclassical Growth Model of being consistent with empirical evidence and the inability of the model to show mechanism through which government policies can influence the growth process, the endogenous growth theory was established which avoids the assumption of exogenous improvement in technology. The endogenous growth model addresses the limitations of the neo-classical model by proposing a variety of channels through which the steady state arises endogenously. To relax the assumption of diminishing returns to capital imposed in the basic neo-classical models, two broad approaches have been followed in the growth literature. The first consists of viewing all production inputs as some form of reproducible capital including physical capital and human capital (Lucas, 1988) or the state of knowledge (Romer, 1986). Secondly, an approach was formulated to generate growth endogenously consisting of the introduction of spillover effects or externalities in the growth process. Romer (1986) models technological growth as the outcome of competitive firms that allowed this was that while individual firms face diminishing returns to investment in knowledge, at the social level, returns to knowledge can be increasing, therefore knowledge is a function of the entire capital stock of the economy. This is so because knowledge can have positive externalities as the center of the growth process.

Romer (1986) developed these ideas into a competition equilibrium model which yields long-run positive growth. The model also suggests that the competitive growth rate is below the socially optimal level due to the presence of knowledge externalities. The accumulation of human capital and its effects on the productivity of the economy has been emphasized in the growth literature as a source of externality. Lucas (1988), in a model built upon the idea that individual workers have more capital, provides one of the best attempts to incorporate the spillover impacts of human capital accumulation. The major significance of the external effect encompassed in the model presented by Lucas (1988) is that under a purely competitive equilibrium, its presence leads to an underinvestment in human capital. The equilibrium growth rate is thus, lower than the optimal growth rate due to the existence of these externalities.

2.3 Empirical Literature Review

The desire to understand the systematic relationship between exchange rate and growth has resulted in a volume of empirical studies which have taken different

dimensions of policy relevance in the literature. Hooper and Kohlhagen (1978) examined the effect of exchange rate unpredictability on price and international trade between the United States and Germany. The study was conducted in the period 1965-1975 and the found that uncertainty regarding exchange rates has an adverse impact on trade but a positive impact on the price of products where the exporters is a risk-lover. Inconsistent negative effect on market price was found in the case of importers where uncertainty is measured as the standard deviation of spot and forward exchange rates over three months. (Cushman 1986; Peree and Steinherr 1989) emphasized that in industrialized countries uncertainty of exchange rates reduced international trade. According to European Commission (1990) and IMF (1984), empirical evidence in favor of a systematic positive (or negative) effect of exchange rate stability on trade (growth rate) in small open economics has remained mixed. In a sample of 95 less developed economies, Dollar (1992) examined whether the volatility of the exchange rate influence the real economy and conducted a negative impact of investment on growth.

Bosworth, Collins and Yuchin (1995) provided evidence that in a large sample of industrial and developing countries, real exchange rate volatility hampers economic growth and reduces productivity growth. The decrease in investment has a negative impact on economic performance. According to the study of Campa and Goldberg (1995), who examined the effect of exchange rate volatility in US manufacturing sectors, it reported a negative effect on investment because the industries with high markup absorb fluctuation of the exchange rate by refusing real investment. The study by Obstfeld and Rogoff (1998) at the theoretical level posit that uncertainty on exchange rates and monetary policies followed by the government reducing the nominal interest rate and in turn causing an appreciation of the home currency can be deleterious for the home economy. Darby et al. (1999) assessed the effect of exchange rate uncertainty on investment in five developed countries-France, Germany, Italy, the United Kingdom, and the United States-by using the Dixit-Pindyck model and reported a significant negative effect on investment. Ubokudom (1999) examined the issues surrounding the implementation of SAP in Nigeria and drew up a conclusion that the peculiar features of the Nigerian economy reduced the efficacy of currency depreciation in producing desirable effects. From the study of the relationship between exchange rate variables and the growth of domestic output in Nigeria (1971-1995), he expressed growth of domestic output as a linear function of variables in the average nominal exchange rate. He further used dummy variables to capture the periods of currency depreciation. The empirical result showed that all coefficient of the major explanatory variables have negative signs. The study by Bleaney and Greenaway (2001) in 14 sub-Saharan African countries during the period 1980-1995 found that exchange rate volatility effects investment but not economic growth.

Bleaney and Greenaway (2001) examined the impact of terms of trade and real exchange rate volatility on investment and growth in 14 sub-Saharan African

countries from 1980 to 1995. The authors observed that growth is negatively influenced of terms of trade volatility while investment is adversely affected by real exchange rate volatility. Odusola and Akinlo (2001), found a mixed result on the impacts of the exchange rate depreciation on output in Nigeria. In the medium and long term, exchange rate depreciation exerted an expansionary impact on output but in the short run, exchange rate depreciation does not expand output. Some studies focus on the impact of exchange rate on growth in which case Bailiu, Lafrance and Perault (2002), observed that exchange rate regimes whether they are pegged, intermediate or flexible, exert a positive influence on economic growth. The study by Frankel and Rose (2002) examined the effect of currency union on trade and output using data over 200 countries and suggested that a currency union is beneficial for all countries as part of the trade. They concluded that for every one percent increase in total trade, common currency increased income per capita by at least one third of a percent.

Devereux and Engel (2003) state that the effect of exchange rate volatility on the welfare of the economy depends on how prices are set. The fluctuation of macroeconomic factors and the dynamic nature of the business environment cause exchange rate volatility. Kandil (2004) examined the effect of fluctuations in exchange rate on output growth and inflation in 22 developing countries. The author discovered that in the long run, exchange rate fluctuations significantly cause output growth and inflation to decrease and increase respectively. Kyreme, (2004) found a significant long-run relationship between real output growth and the exchange rate regardless of the kind of regime. Azid, Jamil, and Kousar (2005) employed data from the manufacturing sector and the GARCH model to examine the impact of exchange rate volatility on economic performance in Pakistan. The results of their study suggest a positive but insignificant impact of exchange rate fluctuations on manufacturing output performance. Dubas and Lee (2005), both found a robust relationship between exchange rate stability and growth. De Grauwe and Schnabl (2005) employed the Generalized Least Squares (GLS) and Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) panel methodology on a dataset comprising of countries in the Central and Eastern Europe. The study found that there is a strong negative relationship between exchange rate volatility and economic growth.

Azid, Jamil and Kasour (2005) found that exchange rate volatility does not have significant impact on manufacturing production in Pakistan between 1973 and 2003. Aghion et al (2006) in his study also found that the effect of exchange rate volatility, which is the consequence of how well the economy is managed on real activity is relatively small and insignificant. The study by Bagella *et al.* (2006) established that countries with flexible exchange rate have more advantages because they absorb stocks more easily than countries with fixed exchange rate. In this way countries that implement flexible exchange rate regimes have a favorable economic performance and fluctuation of the exchange rate promotes their growth. Salami (2006) found that exchange rate is the most important variable that affects private foreign investment in

Nigeria of all other Macroeconomics variable. Empirical evidence has shown strong effect of short-run and long adverse effects of exchange rate swings on economic growth performance through the trade channel.

The nature of the effect, however runs in either the positive or negative direction. Ogun (2006) studied on the impacts of real exchange rate on growth of non-export in Nigeria, highlighted the effects of real exchange on growth of non-oil export in Nigeria. He employed the standard trade theory model of determinants of export growth and two different measures of real exchange misalignment, one of which entails the deviations of the Purchasing Power Parity (PPP) and the other model which is model based estimation of equilibrium real exchange rate (ERER). He observed that irrespective of the alternative measure of misalignment employed, both real exchange misalignment and volatility adversely affected growth of Nigerian non-oil exports. Dritsakis (2007) investigated the relationship between exports and economic growth based on data from EU, the USA and Japan. The study adopted gross domestic product representing economic growth as the dependent variable, while exports was used as the explanatory variable. He conducted Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Kwiatkowski, Phillips, Schmidt and Shin (KPSS) unit root tests, Johansen and Juselius cointegration test and Granger causality test based on Error Correction Model. The results showed that export had causal effect on economic growth in the EU countries and the USA, but had no effect on GDP in Japan.

Unugbro (2007) observed that exchange rate appreciation stimulates foreign direct investment. Schnabel (2007) investigated the impact of exchange rate volatility on the growth of 41 small open economies in the European Monetary Union (EMU) periphery. The study estimation results showed significant impact of exchange rate volatility on economic growth. The study by Eichengreen (2008) did not find any significant relation between Real Exchange Rate (RER) volatility and growth, it supported the idea that: "keeping it at appropriate levels and avoiding excessive volatility enable a country to exploit its capacity for growth. As it is mentioned by Schnabl (2008), the three channels where exchange rate volatility can enhance economic growth are international trade, foreign direct investment, and macroeconomic stability. The study by Schnabl (2008) establishes an adverse relation between growth and exchange rate volatility for countries in an economic catch-up process where the capital market remains underdeveloped and macroeconomic instability tends to be high. In order to examine the influence of exchange rate instability on economic growth for an annual panel of OECD countries during the period between 1980-2011, the study by also, Rana- Aliyu (2009), in a study carried out in Nigeria, found that the appreciation of exchange rate exerts a positive impact on real economic growth in Nigeria. Although, the appreciation of the exchange rate will result in loss of competitiveness, but since the economy fundamentally does not have the potential to appreciate gains through competitiveness, it is therefore more rewarding when a currency appreciates that

when it depreciates. Because appreciation will dampen inflation, boost domestic investment and savings and enhance the standard of living.

Sarkar and Armor (2009), using the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) technique found a negative relationship between exchange rate and economic growth. This result is consistent with the competitiveness hypothesis, which suggests that exchange rate depreciation boosts productivity growth in the short run. Aghion et al. (2009) extended their study to 83 countries during the period from 1960 to 2000. They found that countries in which the financial market has not developed the negative effects of exchange rate volatility are presented. In developed countries, this negative effect is reduced because they sign hedging instruments to cover risky transactions. In a panel data for 83 countries, Aghion, Bacchetta, Rancieri and Rogoff (2009) found that the impact of exchange rate volatility on the long-term productivity of an economy depends on its level of financial development. For countries with relatively low level of financial development, exchange rate volatility reduces growth while exchange rate volatility has no significant effect on countries with relatively high level of financial development.

Adebisi AND Dauda (2009) using the error correction model argued on the contrary that trade liberalization promoted growth in the Nigerian industrial sector and stabilize the exchange rate market between 1970 and 2006. To them, there as a positive and significant relationship between index of industrial production and real export. A one percent rise in real export increases the index of industrial production by 12.2 percent. By implication, it means the policy of deregulation impacted positively on export through exchange rate depreciation. David, Umeh and Ameh (2010) also examined the effect of exchange rate fluctuations on Nigeria manufacturing industry. They employed multiple regression econometric tools which revealed a negative relationship between exchange rate volatility on economic growth shrinks in countries with higher levels of development. Mukhtar and Malik (2010) used the time series data from 1060 to 2007 as well as cointegration and vector error correction model (VECM) to examine the effect of real exchange rate on the growth of three South Asian countries (India, Parkistan and Sri Lanka). The results of the estimation show that real exchange rate volatility exerts a significant negative effect on exports in both the short run and long run. Negative effect was examined by Holland et al. (2011) in a set of 82 advanced and emerging economies. They suggested that economic growth can increase faster when the exchange rate is stable than when the exchange rate is misaligned.

Holland, Vieira, Silva and Bottecchia (2011) evaluated the impact of real exchange rate volatility on growth for developed and emerging economies between 1970 and 2011. They found that high exchange rate volatility impacts positively on economic growth while low exchange rate volatility impacts negatively. Holland et al. (2011) observed that, high (low) exchange rate volatility positively (negatively) affects real GDP growth rate. The study noted that controlling for exchange rate volatility in a model containing levels of exchange rate and exchange rate misalignment renders

the variables insignificant, thereby suggesting that exchange rate stability is more crucial in propelling long-run growth than exchange rate misalignments. The study, however, did not find any significant link between exchange rate volatility and long-run productivity growth. Also, study carried out by Polodoo, Seetanah and Padachi (2011) on the “impact of exchange rate volatility on economic growth on small island developing states” using the generalized method of moments found out that in dynamic setting, volatile exchange rates do not influence economic growth. Another study by Holland, Vieira, Silva and Bottecchia (2011) examined exchange rate volatility on economic growth in 82 advanced and emerging economies using panel econometrics analysis discovered that a relatively less volatile real exchange rate structure has a positive effect on economic growth and vice-versa.

Ndambendia and Alhayky (2011) investigated the long-run relationship between effective real exchange rate volatility and economic growth of 15 sub-Saharan African countries from 1980 to 2004 using the Fully Modified Ordinary Least Square (FMOLS) method. They found that real effective exchange rate volatility adversely affects economic growth when domestic credit-GDP ratio falls below the threshold value of 57%. They concluded that the countries with less-developed financial sector tend to be more negatively affected by effective real exchange rate volatility. Polodoo, Seetanah and Padachi (2011) examined the impact of exchange rate volatility on economic performance of 15 small island developing states, using annual data covering the period 1999 to 2010. Their study model was specified to determine the causality link between exchange rate volatility on one hand, and GDP, FDI and external trade on the other. Using OLS and Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) techniques for data, they found that exchange rate fluctuations impacted positively on economic growth, negatively on external trade, but no impact on FDI. On the effect of exchange rate on the economic sector output.

Ehinomen and Oladipo (2012) examined the impact of exchange rate management on the growth of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria. Ordinary Least Square (OLS) multiple regression analysis was employed to analyze time series data which spanned between 1986 to 2010. The empirical result of this study showed that depreciation which forms part of the structural adjustment programme (SAP), 1986, and which dominated the period under review has no significant relationship with the manufacturing sector's productivity. It was observed that in Nigeria, exchange rate appreciation has a significant relationship with domestic output and recommended that government should direct its exchange rate management policy towards exchange rate appreciation in order to reduce the cost of production in the manufacturing sector which depends heavily on foreign inputs, while there should be total ban of importation on consumer and intermediate goods that can be produced locally.

Oyovwi (2012) investigated the effect of exchange rate fluctuations on economic growth in Nigeria using secondary data from 1970 to 2009. The study employed ADF unit root test, co-integration test and Generalized Auto Regressive Conditional

Heteroscedasticity (GARCH) technique as tools for data analysis. The results showed that exchange rate had positive effect on economic growth in the short run, but the impact was negative in the long run. Pokhariyal, Pundo and Musyoki (2012) used GMM to evaluate the impact of real exchange rate volatility on the economic growth of Kenya. The study found that real exchange rate volatility has a negative impact on economic growth. Dickson (2012) evaluated the effect of exchange rate volatility on Nigeria's economic growth from 1970 to 2009. The author found that in the short run, exchange rate volatility positively impacts on economic growth while in the long run, economic growth negatively responds to exchange rate volatility. In Nigeria, Akpan and Atan (2012) furthered the study on this issue using the GMM to investigate the effects of exchange rate movements on economic growth in Nigeria. They argued that there was no evidence to suggest a strong direct link between exchange rate and output growth. Instead, monetary variables have been responsible for Nigeria economic growth.

Gash, Moses and Musyoki (2012) examined the impact of real exchange rate volatility on economic growth in Kenya. The study employed the Generalized Autoregressive Condition of Heteroscedasticity (GARCH) and computation of the unconditional standard deviation of the changes to measure volatility and Generalized Method Moments (GMM) to assess the impact of the real exchange rate volatility on economic growth for the period, January 1993 to December 2009. Data for the study were collected from Kenya National Bureau of Statistics, Central Bank of Kenya and International Monetary Fund Database by taking monthly frequency. The study found that RER was very volatile for the entire study period. Kenya's RER generally exhibited appreciating and volatility trend, implying that in general, the country's international competitiveness deteriorated over the study period. The RER volatility reflected a negative impact on economic growth of Kenya. Examining the effect of exchange rate shocks on economic growth in Turkey for the period 1987:3.

Berument *et al.* (2012) used sign restriction approach to divide exchange rate shocks in monetary policy fluctuations and portfolio preference fluctuations. The study estimated models where real GDP is dependent in nominal GDP, GDP deflators, exchange rate, interest rate and money supply, using the Vector Autoregressive (VAR) technique. The study found no clear relationship between exchange rate shocks and economic growth but concluded that economic growth depended on the sources of exchange rate shocks. Using time-series data spanning from 1971 to 2009, Mori, Asid, Lily, Mulok and Loganathan (2012) investigated the effects of exchange rates on economic growth in Malaysia. The results of ARDL bounds test suggest that long-run co-integration exists between both nominal and real exchange rates and economic growth with a significant positive coefficient recorded for real exchange rate. The study concluded that both exchange rates have a similar causal effect towards economic growth and suggested that a systematic exchange rate via monetary policy should be properly developed to promote the stability and sustainability of economic growth in Malaysia.

Azeez, Kolapo and Ajayi (2012) also examined the effect of exchange rate volatility on macroeconomic performance in Nigeria from 1986 to 2010. The model formulated depicts Real GDP as the dependent variable, while Exchange Rate (EXR), Balance of Payment (BOP) and Oil Revenue (OREV) are proxies as independent variables. It employed the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) and Johansen co-integration estimation techniques to test for the short and long run effects respectively. The results showed that oil revenue and balance of payment exert negative effects, while exchange rate volatility contributes positively to GDP in the long run. The study recommended that monetary authorities should pursue policies that would curb inflation and ensure stability of exchange rate.

Using Vector Error Correction Model (VECM), Akinlo and Lawal (2012) examined the impact of exchange rate on industrial production in Nigeria over the period 1986-2010. The findings confirmed the existence of long run relationship between industrial production index and exchange rate, money supply and inflation rate. Moreover, exchange rate volatility had no perceptible impact on industrial production in the short run but had positive impact in the long run. Based on the annual time series data for the period 1970 to 2009 and employing vector-autoregressive model, Dada and Oyeranti (2012) analyzed the impact of exchange rate on macroeconomic aggregate in Nigeria. The estimation results showed that there was no evidence of a strong direct relationship between changes in the exchange rate and growth. Rather, Nigeria's economic growth has been directly affected by fiscal and monetary policies and other economic variables particularly the growth of exports (oil) and concluded that improvements in exchange rate management were necessary but not adequate to revive the Nigerian economy.

Musyoki *et al.* (2012) used the monthly frequency data, the GARCH model to capture the real exchange rate volatility and Generalized Method Moments (GMM) to examine the impact of the real exchange rate volatility on the Kenya's economic growth for the period January 1993 to December 2009. They reported persistent volatility throughout the study period and the negative influence of real exchange rate volatility on the Kenyan economic growth. Tarawalie *et al.* (2012) investigated the effects of exchange rate volatility on output growth and inflation in the West African Monetary Zone (consisting of Ghana, the Gambia, Guinea, Liberia, Nigeria and Sierra Leone) following exchange rate regime shift. Results from the study revealed that, while exchange rate volatility is inflationary across all the countries, its effects on output growth differ. Specifically, volatility and depreciation in particular negatively affect real GDP growth in Liberia and Sierra Leone but positively impacts on output in the other countries albeit weakly. The difference in direction and magnitude of effect is not far-fetched from the differences in macroeconomic conditions prevailing in each country. Examining the impact of real exchange rate volatility on long-run economic growth for advanced and emerging economies over the period 1970-2009.

Akpan and Atan (2012) examined the impact of exchange rate fluctuation on real output growth in Nigeria using quarterly time series data spanning 1986 to 2010. The study employed simultaneous equation model and Generalized Method Moments (GMM) technique for data analysis. The results showed evidence of a strong causal link between exchange rate fluctuations and real output growth. The study concluded that adequate efforts have not been made in the exchange rate management regime to pull the country out of economic decline. Jamil *et al.* (2012) examined the effect of volatility on growth during two periods for eleven European countries in the European Monetary Union and four countries that did not adopt the Euro as a common currency.

Using GARCH Models, Dahiru and Asemota (2013) examined exchange rate volatility with monthly exchange rate return series from 1985 to 2011 for Naira/US dollar return and from 2004 to 2011 for Naira/British Pounds and Naira/Euro returns. The study compared estimates of variants of GARCH models with break in respect of the US dollar rates with exogenously determined break points. The results revealed presence of volatility in the three currencies and equally indicate that most of the asymmetric models rejected the existence of a leverage effect except for models with volatility break. Evaluating the models through standard information criteria, volatility persistence and the log likelihood statistic, showed that results improved with estimation of volatility models with breaks as against those of GARCH models without volatility breaks and that the introduction of volatility breaks reduces the level of persistence in most of the models. In the same vein, Danmola (2013) analyzed the impact of exchange rate volatility on macro-economic variables in Nigeria. The ordinary least square and Granger Causality was used to test the relationship between them. The variables used were exchange rate, GDP and investment. It was observed that exchange rate has a significant impact on economic growth. The study then recommended exchange rate control.

Gadanecz and Mehrotra (2013) revealed non-linearity between real exchange rate volatility and output volatility among emerging market economies. Their finding suggests that real exchange rate volatility aids in absorbing shocks as well as limit output volatility, but too much of volatility in exchange rate increases output volatility. Obansa, Okoroafor, Aluko and Millicent (2013) also examined the relationship between exchange rate and economic growth in Nigeria from 1970-2010. The result indicated that exchange rate has a strong impact on economic growth. They concluded that exchange rate liberalization was good for the Nigerian economy as it promotes economic growth.

Similarly, Danmola (2013) used the ordinary least square (OLS) regression technique and the Granger Causality test to analyze the impact of exchange rate variability on economic growth proxy as GDP in Nigeria for the period 1980-2010. The study found that exchange rate variability showed a significant positive relationship with economic growth. For studies concluded on other developing countries, Attah-Obeng, Enu, Osei-Gyimah and Opoku (2013) examined the

relationship between GDP growth rate and exchange rate in Ghana from the period 1980 to 2012. The study employed the graphing of the scatter diagram for the two variables which are GDP growth rate and exchange rate, established the correlation between GDP growth rate and exchange rate using the Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) and finally estimated the simple linear regression using Ordinary Least Square (OLS). This result conformed with the theory that undervaluation (high exchange rate) stimulates economic growth in the short run. Thus, policy makers should stabilize monetary and fiscal policies in the long run.

Adeniran, Yusuf and Adeyemi (2014) examined the impact of exchange rate on Nigerian economic growth from 1986 to 2013. Employing the correlation and regression analysis, the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) method was used to analyze the data. The result revealed that exchange rate has positive and insignificant impact on Nigerian economic growth and recommended that government should encourage the export promotion strategies in order to maintain a surplus balance of trade and also conducive environment, adequate security, effective fiscal and monetary policies, as well as infrastructural facilities should be provided so that foreign investors will be attracted to invest in Nigeria.

Basirat, Nasirpour and Jorjorzadeh (2014) examined the effect of exchange rate fluctuation on economic growth in developing countries using data for 18 countries from 1986 to 2010. Ayinde (2014) examined the impact of exchange rate volatility on the performance of the manufacturing sector of Nigeria between 1986 and 2012. Employing the Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity (GARCH) approach, the study revealed that exchange rate volatility did not significantly affect the sector. Mehdi, Arezoo and Alireza (2014) assessed the effect of exchange rate fluctuations on the growth of 18 developing economies between 1986 and 2010 and found that exchange rate fluctuation has a significant negative impact on economic growth. The study variables include economic growth (response variable), exchange rate and financial development (explanatory variables). Data for the study was collected from World Development Indicators on World Bank website. The study conducted unit root test based on Lin, Levin and Chu model; Im, Pesaran and Shin model; as well as ADF/PP test; and found that exchange rate had significant negative effect on economic growth. The results are mixed for countries in the analysis, but the common currency decreases the harmful impact of exchange rate volatility on industrial production (Janus and Riera-Crichton 2015). Moreover, for Germany and Denmark, the impact of exchange rate volatility was negative for both periods, before and after the introductions of a common currency. Janus and Riera-Crichton (2015) employed Instrumental Variables estimation (IV) and showed that real effective exchange rate volatility is negatively associated with economic growth.

Unah (2015) examined the effect of exchange rate volatility on economic growth in Nigeria on the basis of annual data from 1980 to 2012. Employing the Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity (GARCH) technique to generate exchange rate volatility, the relationship between exchange rate volatility and

economic growth was estimated. Findings further showed that in the short run, economic growth is negatively responsive to exchange rate volatility in Nigeria case, while in the long run, a negative relationship exists between the two variables. The study recommended control of impact content of both public and private expenditure, greater diversification of the economy through investment in key productive sectors of the economy to guard against the vicissitude exchange rate volatility. Apollos, Emmanuel and Olusegun (2015) adopted the OLS technique and data for the period 1986-2013 to investigate the relationship between the GDP and exchange rate, imports, exports and the inflation rate in Nigeria. The result of their study revealed a significant positive relationship between the GDP and the explanatory variables like the exchange rate and exports. Azu and Nasiri (2015) investigated the impact of exchange rate fluctuation on sustainable economic growth in Nigeria using quarterly secondary data from 2004 to 2014. The variables used in their study include GDP (response variables), real exchange rate, exports, imports foreign direct investment and foreign reserves. Data for the study variables were sourced from the IMF database, CBN Statistical Bulletin, and United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) data centre. They employed ADF and Philip-Perron unit root test and VAR technique for the analysis of data. The study found that GDP was positively controlled by real exchange rate, foreign reserves and foreign direct investment.

Adelowokan, Adesoye and Balogun (2015) utilized the Vector Error Correction Mechanism (VECM) to determine the effect of exchange rate volatility on investment and economic growth in Nigeria from 1986 to 2014. Their results showed that exchange rate volatility negatively affects investment and growth. Mehta (2015) examined the link between exports, imports, and economic growth in India using secondary data covering the period 1976 to 2014. The study adopted GDP representing economic growth as the dependent variable, while exports and imports were used as the independent variables. Using unit root test, Engle Granger co-integration and Vector Error Correction Models for the analysis of data, the study found that a significant relationship existed between exports, imports and economic growth in India. Also, Ucan (2016) examined the relationship between export and economic growth in Turkey using quarterly time series data from 2006 to 2015. The study used gross domestic product representing economic growth as the dependent variable. While exports were adopted as the independent variables. He employed Johansen co-integration and Granger Causality tests as the statistical tools for the analysis of data. The results revealed unidirectional causality link between exports and economic growth. Meaning that increase in exports resulted to increase in economic growth, but improvements in the economy did not affect exports.

Using GMM, Alagidede and Ibrahim (2016) found exchange rate volatility to be negatively related to Ghana's economic growth between 1980 and 2013. Isola, Oluwafunke, Victor, and Asaley (2016) employed the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model to investigate the linkage between exchange rate volatility and

economic growth in Nigeria from 2003-2013 and the results indicate that there is no relationship between the variables in the long run. One concern with some of the data studies that used the OLS model is that they failed to account for the panel effects of the data used and the issue with the endogeneity of the variable in the study. Danladi and Uba (2016) assessed the impact of exchange rate volatility on the economic performance of Ghana and Nigeria from 1980 to 2013. The GARCH analysis revealed that exchange rate volatility as a significant negative effect on the performance of both economic. Etale and Etale (2016) evaluated the relationship between exports, FDI and economic growth in Malaysia using time series data spanning 1980 to 2013. Gross domestic product (GDP) representing economic growth was regressed as a function of exports and FDI. The study utilized unit root test, co-integration test and VECM based on Granger causality test to evaluate data. The results among other provided authorities adopt appropriate exchange rate regime for the country to achieve meaningful economic development.

Alkhateeb, Mahmood and Saultan (2016) examined the link between exports and economic growth in Saudi Arabia using annual data from 1980 to 2013. The study adopted gross domestic product (as the dependent variable) and proxy for economic growth, while the independent variables include exports, imports, real exchange rate and foreign direct investment. Data on the study variables, collected from the Saudi Arabian Monetary Agency, were analyzed using ADF/PP unit root test, co-integration test and VECM. The results proved that a two-way impact link existed between exports and economic growth. They therefore recommended that Saudi Arabia should pursue a policy of trade liberalization.

Dritsakis and Stamatiou (2016) investigated the link between trade openness and economic growth in 30 EU member countries using secondary data covering 1995 to 2013. The study adopted GDP (proxy for economic growth) as the response variable, while trade openness was used as the explanatory variable. They employed unit root test, co-integration test and error correction mechanism based on Granger Causality test in the evaluation of data. They found that trade openness had a positive impact on economic growth. Ismaila (2016), examined exchange rate depreciation and Nigerian economic performance after structural adjustment programme (SAP). The study used co-integration and error correction mechanism. The variables used were broad money supply, net export and total government expenditure, real output and exchange rate. The results show that broad money supply, net export and total government expenditure have significant impact on real output performance in the long run, while exchange rate has direct and insignificant effect on the Nigerian economic growth in both short and long run. Therefore, the study suggested that policy makers should not totally rely on exchange rate depreciation policy instrument to induce economic growth.

Hamdan (2016) examined the impacts of exports and imports on economic growth in 17 Arab Nations using annual data from 1995 to 2013. The study adopted GDP, proxy for economic growth as the dependent variable, while export and import were used as

the independent variables. The results of data analysis showed evidence that export and import had positive effect on economic growth. Theoretical literature on exchange rate volatility nexus economic growth is still a big debate among economists. The appreciation of currency happens by an upward movement while a downward movement indicates a loss in value (depreciation) against foreign currency (Anyanwu *et al.* 2007). Theories that explain this up and down movement in the exchange rate are the real option theory, the interest rate parity theory, purchasing power parity, traditional flow theory etc. thus, the exchange rate volatility as an indicator of uncertainty explains the behavior of investor decisions. Stable exchange rates become more attractive for firms that decide to increase their investment. Therefore, the real option theory is used to examine the nexus between rate volatility and economic growth by researchers. The empirical literature regarding the effect of exchange rate volatility on economic growth is unsettled and reviewing literature concern on channels where the exchange rate volatility affects the real economy is crucial.

Similarly, Alper 2017 examined the impact of exchange rate volatility on Turkey's trade to the 15 European countries during 2002-2013 by using Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity (GARCH) (1, 0) for calculating volatility. GARCH model is a statistical model that is considered as a reliable model for time series data to calculate volatility. The findings from Alper (2017) are that exchange rate volatility reduces export flows in the short-run. However, the effect for import sectors is both positive and negative in the long run. Iyeli and Utting (2017) assessed the effect of exchange rate volatility on Economic Growth in Nigeria from 1970 to 2011. The model formulated depicts Real GDP as the dependent variable, while Exchange Rate (EXR), Balance of Payment (BOP) Oil Revenue (OREV) and inflation (INF) are independent variables. The study employed the Johansen C0-integration estimation techniques to test for the short and long runs effect of the variables used. The ADF test revealed that all the variables are stationary. From the parsimonious model, the results show that OREV and EXR are positively related to GDP. Further findings revealed that there exist two equations at 5% level in both trace and Max-Eigen statistic. This implies that exchange rate volatility and oil revenue contribute positively to GDP in the long run.

Arshad and Usman (2017) examined the impact of export on economic growth in Pakistan using time series data covering 1992 to 2015. The study adopted GDP as proxy for economic growth and the dependent variable, while export, foreign reserves and FDI were used as independent variables. They made use of regression analysis based on E-views software, unit root test, Johansen co-integration test and Granger Causality test to analyze data obtained from World Development Indicators and IMF database. The results indicated that export and foreign reserves had significant positive effect on GDP (the proxy for economic growth). Bakari and Mabrouki (2016) investigated the nexus between exports, imports and economic growth in Turkey using annual data covering 1960 to 2015. Data for study was

obtained from World Development Indicators 2016. Data was evaluated based on unit root test, Johansen co-integration test and Vector Auto Regression Model. The study found that there was no auto correlation between the three variables. However, the study provided strong evidence of one-way causality movement from exports to economic growth as well as imports to economic growth.

Dal Bianco and Loan (2017) worked on the influence of price and real exchange rate volatility on foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows for 10 Latin American and Caribbean countries. This study used GARCH techniques and data for the period 1990 and 2012. FDI, measured as a percentage of GDP, was used as dependent variable, and the independent variables were price and real exchange rate volatility, institutional quality (i.e., political freedom) capita Gross Domestic Product, trade openness (in % of GDP), human capital (i.e., literacy rate), and infrastructural development (i.e., number of the telephone lines). The authors considered that the exchange rate volatility has a negative influence on FDI inflows in this region and price volatility seems not to be relevant for the countries analyzed. There are several studies focused on the relationship between exchange rate volatility, international trade and foreign direct investment, taking into account the connection between trade and capital flows at the international level.

Bahmani-Oskooee and Gelan (2018) employed the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model in their study in order to investigate the effect of exchange rate risk on trade flows in the short-run and long-run for twelve African countries during the period 1971Q1-2015Q4. The ARDL method has advantages in forecasting compared to other techniques based on co-integration. The volatility of the exchange rate improves or worsens exports and imports, but in the short run, the effect is more prevalent (Senadza and Diaba 2018). In addition, Turkey's trade with European Union countries is not affected by the volatility of exchange rates. Latief and Lefen (2018) used GARCH models to analyze the nexus between exchange rate volatility and international trade and foreign direct investment (FDI). The sample consists of seven developing countries (Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Maldives, Nepal, Pakistan, and Sri Lanka) and statistical data were collected for the period 1995-2016. The results of the study demonstrated the importance of the specificities of the countries. For countries like Bhutan, Maldives, and Nepal, the exchange rate volatility significantly positively affected international trade, but for countries like Pakistan, the impact on international trade had significant negative impact. While, the exchange rate volatility measured with TGARCH showed a significant positive impact on international trade for the countries such as Bhutan, Maldives, and Nepal. Regarding the relation of exchange rate volatility and FDI, for India and Pakistan, the impact was significantly positive, but for Bhutan and Nepal, the influence significantly negative.

Akinmulegun and Falana (2018) examined the effect of exchange rate fluctuation on industrial output in Nigeria using data covering 1986 to 2015. The study adopted gross domestic product representing industrial output growth as the response

variable, while the explanatory variable includes exchange rate, inflation, interest rate and net exports. Data was sourced from the National Bureau of Statistics and CBN Statistics Bulletin. Statistical tools used for data analysis include ADF/PP unit root test, Johansen co-integration test, Pairwise Granger Causality test and VECM. The results showed a unidirectional causality from exchange rate to industrial output growth, that is, industrial output responded significantly positively to exchange rate much more than the other variables. The study concluded that exchange rate had potentials of affecting industrial output growth in Nigeria.

Ufoeze, Okuma, Nwakoby and Alajekwu (2018) investigated the effect of exchange rate fluctuation on economic growth in Nigeria using time series data covering 1970 to 2012. The study adopted exchange rate, inflation, money supply and oil revenue as the explanatory variables, while gross domestic product (proxy for economic growth) was used as the response variable. Secondary data for the study were obtained from CBN Statistical Bulletin. They employed multiple regression technique based on OLS for the analysis of data. Their study produced mixed findings, and they concluded that floating exchange rate outperformed fixed exchange rate as a better indicator of sustainable economic growth.

Barcuellil *et al.* (2018) examined the impact of exchange rate volatility on economic growth. An empirical investigation based on a sample of 45 developing and emerging countries over the period of 1985 to 2015 was conducted using the difference and system generalized method moments estimators. Findings suggested that the generalized autoregressive conditional heteroskedasticity-based measure of nominal and real exchange rate volatility has a negative impact on economic growth. Also, the effect of exchange rate volatility depends on the exchange rate regimes and financial openness, that is, volatility is more harmful when countries adopt flexible exchange rate regimes and financial openness.

Bostan and Firtescu (2019) conducted a study regarding the influence of the exchange rate on international commercial trade competitiveness of Romania. The study used statistical data for the period 2007-2014 and Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression is employed. Variables such as exchange rate, inflation, investment and interest rate are considered as exogenous, while Romanian exports and imports are endogenous variables. They concluded that the exchange rate is an important determinant of competitiveness, but the influence of uncertainty on export and import is different. This effect seems to be weaker for imports. Also, empirical studies have not reached a consensus on the effect of exchange rate volatility on investment. In some studies, the exchange rate volatility creates uncertainty in the economic environment and decreases investment.

For panel cross country studies, Umaru *et al.* (2019) examined the effects of exchange rate volatility on economic growth of West African English-speaking countries. Macroeconomic data used for this study were obtained from the World Bank Data Stream between 1980 to 2017 and analyzed using State 14 panel data

regression analysis. The results obtained showed that the independent variable (real exchange rate) is statistically significant and negatively related to the dependent variable (GDP) in West African English-speaking countries excluding time-invariant variables.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design and Model Specification

This sub-section deals with the determination of the dependent and independent variables. The specification of the model will be based on information relating to the phenomenon being studied. The main task at this point is to make an attempt to model the relationship between exchange rate volatility and economic growth in Nigeria. The relationship between exchange rate volatility and economic growth can best be determined using VAR models. To effectively capture the complex inter-linkages, Vector autoregressive method is often used since it is a dynamic system that permits simultaneity of activities among variables in the model. In other words, the variables in the system freely express themselves at the same time and the impulse response function serves to trace the impact of actions due to each variable in the entire system. VAR also provides the additional advantage of using the reduced form equations as distinct from large scale methods with numerous variables. Following the Marshall-Lerner (ML) condition, exchange rate depreciation would lead to improvement in economic growth and balance of payments through the expansion of output and export provided that the sum of price elasticity of demand for export and demand for import are greater than unity; we expect depreciation to improve macroeconomic dynamics. Experience has shown that in Nigeria, the monetary authority uses either the quantitative or qualitative measures of stabilizing the macroeconomic activities but most often, money supply, interest rate and inflation rate are the major quantitative measures employed by the Central bank in maintaining a close watch of monetary balance in Nigeria.

However, the exchange rate deepening experienced in the past prompted the monetary authority to strengthen the stock of money reserves in order to decelerate exchange rate volatility and watch the overall economic performance closely in terms of productivity.

3.2.1 Model 1: The Impact of exchange rate volatility on economic growth in Nigeria

We identify major growth variable that could be influenced significantly by fluctuations in the exchange rate and balance of payment; these are money supply, inflation, interest rate, government expenditure, real output, trade openness, unemployment and balance of payments. Here, all these variables are considered in the analysis. Based on the relationship between the variables of interest, we use VAR model to isolate the exogenous component of shocks in the economy described by the structural equation below:

$$G(L)y_t = \epsilon_t \text{-----} (1)$$

In equation 1, y_t is the data vector in the baseline model given by:

[BOP; GDPR; GEX; INF; RIR; M2; OPN; UNEM]. Where BOP is the balance of payments, GDPR is the real output growth, INF is the inflation rate which measures price stability, GEX is the government expenditure, RIR is the interest rate in Nigeria, M2 is the money supply, OPN is the trade openness and UNEM is the unemployment. $G(L)$ is the matrix polynomial in the lag operator, and et is a vector of serially uncorrelated structural disturbances. The structural model is based on the reduced form model below;

$$y_t = G(L)y_t + u_t \text{-----} (2)$$

To recover structural parameters from the reduced form equation, the model uses the generalized non-recursive method that imposes restrictions to identify the structural components of the error terms. The equation below summarizes the identification scheme used.

$$(etExch) = \begin{pmatrix} etBop \\ etGdpr \\ etGex \\ etInf \\ etM2 \\ etOpn \\ etRir \\ etUnem \end{pmatrix} (etExch) \text{-----} (3)$$

3.2.2 Model 2: the casual relationship between exchange rate volatility and economic growth in Nigeria

This model specifies the casual direction between exchange rate volatility and economic growth. The model is to determine the directional causality between exchange rate volatility and economic growth in Nigeria. Causality is assumed when lagged values of a variable Y_i that contains lagged values of Y_i and X_i . Therefore, following the standard pair-wise Granger Causality test to test the direction of causality between exchange rate volatility and economic growth taking cognizance of their integrations, we specify the granger causality in the equations below:

$$\Delta GDPG_{gt} = \sum_{i=1}^m \alpha_i \Delta EXCH_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^m \beta_j \Delta GDPR_{g_{t-j}} + \mu_{1t} \text{-----} (3.1a)$$

$$\Delta EXCH_t = \sum_{i=1}^m \pi_i \Delta GDPR_{g_{t-i}} + \sum_{j=1}^m \delta_j \Delta EXCH_{t-j} + \mu_{2t} \text{-----} (3.2b)$$

Where:

EXCH = Exchange Rate

GDPR = Real Gross Domestic Product

Δ = The First Difference Operator

Σ = Summation

$\alpha, \pi, \beta, \text{ and } \delta$ = Coefficient

I and j = lagged Periods

t = Time

μ_{1t}, μ_{2t} = Error Term

m = Maximum Number of Lags.

3.3 Estimation Technique

First, the stability properties of the variables used in the investigation are investigated in order to determine their order of integration, which ultimately assists in determining the appropriate econometric framework to be present study, i.e., the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and the 2Philips-Perron (PP). The PP unit root test is generally considered to have a greater reliability than the ADF in that it is both robust in the midst of serial correlation and heteroskedasticity.

3.4 Description of Variables

Balance of payment (BOP): The balance of payments (BOP), also known as the balance of international payments, is a statement of all transactions made between entities in one country and the rest of the world over a defined period, such as a quarter or a year. It summarizes all transactions that a country's individuals, Companies and government bodies complete with individuals, companies, and government bodies outside the country.

Real Gross Domestic Product (GDPR): The real economic growth rate, or real GDP growth rate, measures economic growth, as expressed by gross domestic product (GDP), from one period to another, adjusted for inflation or deflation. In order words, it reveals changes in the value of all goods and services produced by an economic – the economic output of a country – while accounting for price fluctuations.

Government Expenditure (GEX): Government spending or expenditure includes all government consumption, investment, and transfer payments. In national income accounting, the acquisition by governments of goods and services for current use, to directly satisfy the individual or collective needs of the community, is classed as government final consumption expenditure. Government acquisition of goods and

services intended to create future benefits, such as infrastructure investment or research spending, is classed as government spending, on final consumption and on gross capital formation, together constitute one of the major components of gross domestic product.

Inflation rate (INF): The inflation rate is a measurement of the rise in price of a good or service over a period of time reflected as a percentage. It is usually measured on a monthly and annual basis. Inflation is an increase in the general level of price across a broad spectrum of products. The opposite of inflation is deflation, which is a decrease in the general price level for goods and services. It's basically a negative rate of inflation.

Money Supply (M2): The money supply is all the currency and other liquid instructions in a country's economy on the date measured. The money supply roughly includes both cash and deposits that can be used almost as easily as cash.

Trade openness (OPN): Trade openness is one measure of the extent to which a country is engaged in the global trading system. Trade openness is usually measured by the ratio between the sum of exports and imports and gross domestic product (GDP).

Real Interest Rate (RIR): A real interest rate is an interest rate that has been adjusted to remove the effects of inflation to reflect the real cost of funds to the borrower and the real yield to the lender or to an investor. The real interest rate reflects the rate of time-preference for current goods over future goods.

Unemployment (UNEM): Percentage of unemployed individuals in an economy among individuals currently in the labour force. It is calculated as $\frac{\text{Unemployed individuals}}{\text{Total Labour Force}} \times 100$ where unemployed individuals are those who are currently not working but are actively seeking for work.

3.5 Source of data

The data were obtained from the statistical bulletin of the central bank of Nigeria. Government expenditure (GEX), Exchange rate (EXCH), Real Gross Domestic Product (GDPR), Money Supply (M2) and Real Interest Rate (RIR). Following standard practice, openness was computed as total trade as a ratio of the sum of export and import to gross domestic product.

4. EMPIRICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Unit Root Tests

Time series data tend to exhibit either a deterministic or stochastic trend and are non-stationary. Prior to testing for the direction of causality between the time series, the first step is to check stationarity of the variable used in the models. The aim of this test is to determine whether the time series have a stationary trend, and if non-stationary, to show the order of integration when non-stationary time series data are used in a

regression model, the result may spuriously indicate significant relationship when they actually do not exist.

Table 4.1. UNIT ROOT TEST

Variables	ADF		PP	
	Constant, Linear, trend	1(d)	Constant, Linear, trend	1(d)
BOP	-5.634592	1(1)***	-12.20254	1(1)***
EXCH	-7.618701	1(1)***	5.979992	1(1)***
GDPR	-4.894079	1(1)***	-26.99828	1(1)***
GEX	-4.894079	1(1)***	-5.867780	1(1)***
INF	-3.385306	1(1)***	-13.79395	1(1)***
M2	-5.626711	1(1)***	-6.419753	1(1)***
OPN	-5.221523	1(1)***	-8.747949	1(1)***
RIR	-8.730690	1(1)***	-20.65946	1(1)***
UNEM	-7.468608	1(1)***	-7.468608	1(1)***

Source: Author's computation using Eviews 9

N/B: *** significant at 1%, 5% and 10%; ** significant at 5% and 10%.

The test of stationarity of the variables using ADF and PP statistics show that all the variables are stationary at 1(1) and at constant, linear and trend level except for inflation that was stationary at constant with ADF. The level of integration of the variables indicates cointegration or long run relationship among the variables.

Table 4.2: Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05	
No. of CE(s)			Critical Value	Prob.**
None*	0.881544	292.4949	197.3709	0.0000
At most 1 *	0.839027	215.6991	159.5297	0.0000
At most 2 *	0.796768	149.9445	125.6154	0.0007
At most 3	0.625717	92.58192	95.75366	0.0810
At most 4	0.508757	57.20313	69.81889	0.3311
At most 5	0.336856	31.61376	47.85613	0.6333
At most 6	0.237442	16.82626	29.79707	0.6529
At most 7	0.158615	7.067510	15.49471	0.5698
At most 8	0.023337	0.850075	3.841466	0.3565

Trace test indicates 3 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

*Denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Table 4.3: Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized		Max-Eigen	0.05	
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Critical Value	Prob, **
None *	0.881544	76.79581	58.43354	0.0003
At most 1 *	0.839027	65.75461	52.36261	0.0013
At most 2 *	0.796768	57.36258	46.23142	0.0023
At most 3	0.625717	35.37879	40.07757	0.1540
At most 4	0.508757	25.58938	33.87687	0.3463
At most 5	0.336856	14.78749	27.58434	0.7648
At most 6	0.237442	9.758754	21.131662	0.7669
At most 7	0.158615	6.217435	14.26460	0.5855
At most 8	0.023337	0.850075	3.841466	0.3565

Source: Author's computation using Eviews 9

Max-eigenvalue test indicates 3 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

*denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

The cointegration test for the variables shows that for trace test and max-eigen value, there are three cointegrating equations each. This is further proof of long-term relationship among the variables.

4.2 Granger Causality Test Result

It is a necessity to know the direction of causality between Exchange rate volatility and economic growth in Nigeria. The Granger causality test result sheds more light on this by using the lag specification as obtained from Eviews 9.

Table 4.4 Pair-wise Granger Causality Tests

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.	Decision	Direction
GDPR does not Granger Cause EXCH	38	0.57184	0.5700	Accept	No Causality
EXCH does not Granger Cause GDPR		0.21697	0.8061	Accept	No Causality

Source: Author's computation using Eviews 9

4.2.1 Test of Hypothesis ($H_0: 1$)

The hypothesis that there is no causal relationship between exchange rate volatility and economic growth is answered based on the result obtained in table 4.2. Using the F-statistic result for the variables and comparing it with the critical value and checking their individual P-values, the null hypothesis is accepted. By this, the decision rule follows that we do not reject the null hypothesis if F-statistic values are less than the critical value. Therefore, since the F-statistic values are all less than the critical value, we do not reject the null hypothesis, hence, concluding that there is no causal relationship between exchange rate volatility and economic growth in

Nigeria. This is in consonance with the work of Eichengreen, (2008).

4.2.2 Test of Hypothesis ($H_0: 2$)

Table 4.5: Response of GDP:

Period	BOP	EXCH	GDP	GEX	INF	M2GDP	OPN	RIR	UNEM
1	-0.607098 (0.344 46)	-0.536322 (0.34127)	4.162433 (0.24032)	0.000000 (0.00000)	0.000000 (0.00000)	0.000000 (0.00000)	0.000000 (0.00000)	0.000000 (0.00000)	0.000000 (0.00000)
2	-0.260231 (0.46865)	-0.542638 (0.47150)	3.579160 (0.42076)	-0.006620 (0.36577)	-0.042417 (0.36897)	-0.062125 (0.36625)	0.016946 (0.36819)	-0.071621 (0.36191)	0.126438 (0.36652)
3	-0.147357 (0.40050)	-0.34 9433 (0.38274)	2.565590 (0.43299)	-0.101068 (0.30234)	0.214534 (0.38442)	0.038399 (0.36673)	0.084340 (0.35055)	-0.008828 (0.3731 0)	0.315927 (0.40284)
4	-0.085178 (0.36584)	-0.166987 (0.33576)	1.804612 (0.45656)	-0.177363 (0.28657)	0.390304 (0.41115)	0.089153 (0.38503)	0.134963 (0.34323)	0.052131 (0.38960)	0.430484 (0.43762)
5	-0.036933 (0.36033)	-0.044943 (0.32029)	1.261991 (0.46428)	-0.220611 (0.28662)	0.453603 (0.44003)	0.113948 (0.41020)	0.1772 57 (0.35998)	0.112312 (0.39462)	0.481211 (0.45037)
6	-0.00 266 (0.35420)	0.034208 (0.31220)	0.878974 (0.44134)	-0.241437 (0.28404)	0.444950 (0.44822)	0.124175 (0.416 45)	0.212444 (0.37260)	0.165557 (0.37317)	0.490128 (0.43013)
7	0.019229 (0.34199)	0.085148 (0.30428)	0.611994 (0.40371)	-0.248929 (0.27581)	0.395930 (0.44113)	0.122896 (0.40512)	0.239739 (0.37663)	0.206596 (0.33700)	0.474666 (0.39497)
8	0.030954 (0.32517)	0.117643 (0.29648)	0.428214 (0.36509)	-0.248832 (0.26426)	0.327 859 (0.42576)	0.113111 (0.38227)	0.259422 (0.37408)	0.234178 (0.29780)	0.446454 (0.35903)
9	0.034606 (0.30616)	0.138285 (0.28963)	0.303319 (0.33215)	-0.244813 (0.2519 0)	0.254467 (0.40656)	0.097763 (0.35315)	0.272465 (0.36729)	0.249470 (0.26256)	0.412538 (0.32824)
10	0.032120 (0.28680)	0.151447 (0.28399)	0.219503 (0.30631)	-0.239109 (0.24036)	0.184079 (0.38617)	0.079385 (0.32155)	0.280096 (0.35789)	0.254718 (0.23411)	0.376986 (0.30327)

Source: Author's computation using Eviews 9

The response of economic growth to exchange rate shock is presented in the table above. From the first quarter up to the fifth quarter, a reduction in economic growth of 53%, 54%, 34%, 16% and 4% is noticed due to exchange rate shock. A gradual increase of 3% is observed in the 6th quarter. This improved to 8%, 11%, 13% and 15% in the 7th, 8th, 9th and 10th quarter respectively. It can therefore be said that exchange rate fluctuations have both negative as well as positive impact on economic growth. However, the rate of negative impact outweighs that of the positive impact. This result is in line with the work of Dollar (1992).

4.2.3 Test of Hypothesis (H0:3)

Table 4.6: Response of BOP:

Period	BOP	EXCH	GDPR	GEX	INF	M2GDP	OPN	RIR	UNEM
1	2.296400 (0.13258)	0.000000 (0.000000)	0.000000 (0.000000)						
2	1.868123 (0.22464)	- (0.19990)	0.121636 (0.19858)	- (0.19805)	0.031918 (0.19977)	0.051022 (0.19829)	- (0.19930)	0.001428 (0.19589)	0.0014 (0.198)
3	1.544445 (0.20289)	- (0.17116)	0.480523 (0.21610)	- (0.15734)	- (0.20201)	- (0.19248)	- (0.18281)	-0.033635 (0.195221)	0.1368 (0.211)
4	1.292489 (0.21566)	0.011264 (0.18809)	0.710796 (0.25239)	- (0.17113)	- (0.23293)	- (0.21902)	- (0.19798)	-0.070344 (0.21882)	0.2432 (0.211)
5	1.064724 (0.23569)	0.059294 (0.20822)	0.844296 (0.28016)	- (0.18710)	- (0.26632)	- (0.24979)	- (0.22348)	-0.103379 (0.23899)	0.3035 (0.268)
6	0.863172 (0.25143)	0.119557 (0.22443)	0.908395 (0.29490)	- (0.20030)	- (0.29174)	- (0.27300)	- (0.24633)	-0.128951 (0.24903)	0.3310 (0.282)
7	0.685965 (0.26251)	0.183028 (0.23647)	0.920515 (0.30204)	- (0.20986)	- (0.31077)	- (0.28896)	- (0.26557)	-0.145414 (0.25256)	0.3371 (0.289)
8	0.530868 (0.26948)	0.244237 (0.24531)	0.895060 (0.30495)	- (0.21636)	- (0.32475)	- (0.29883)	- (0.28138)	-0.152901 (0.25227)	0.3298 (0.292)
9	0.396057 (0.27300)	0.299661 (0.25179)	0.843413 (0.30503)	- (0.22043)	- (0.33440)	- (0.30349)	- (0.29403)	-0.152206 (0.24947)	0.3145 (0.294)
10	0.279869 (0.27357)	0.347208 (0.25647)	0.774442 (0.30274)	- (0.22259)	- (0.34020)	- (0.30360)	- (0.30365)	-0.144454 (0.24471)	0.2945 (0.293)

Source: Author's computation using Eview 9

The response of balance of payment to exchange rate volatility is presented above. It is seen that in the first quarter, there was no significant response of balance of payments to exchange rate shock. In the second quarter, there was a reduction of balance of payments by 5%. This further deteriorated to 1% in the third quarter but increase by 1% in the fourth quarter. The response of BOP to exchange rate shock

increase 5% in the fifth quarter and the 11% in the sixth quarter. Continuous increase in BOP to 18%, 24%, 29%, and 35% is noticed in the seventh to tenth quarter. What this implies is that, Nigeria had unfavorable balance of payments of 1% in the fourth quarter up to 34% in the tenth quarter. This finding supports the work of Oladipupo (2011).

4.3 Impulse Response Function

Impulse response function is determined through an in-depth impulse response analysis that helps to quantify the reaction of every single variable in the model on an exogenous shock to the model. The reaction is usually measured for every variable at a given time a shock occurs. The reaction of another economic variable to the impulse is referred to as the response.

Figure 1: Response of variables to one standard shock in exchange rate

5. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary

This study was principally designed to analyze the impact of exchange rate volatility on economic growth in Nigeria from 1970-2020. In a bid to achieve this objective, the Vector Autoregressive (VAR) model was used. Time series data were collected from the publications of Central Bank of Nigeria, World development indicators and National Bureau of statistics. The properties of the data were analyzed using Philip Peron (PP) Unit Root Test and ADF, the result revealed that Balance of payment (BOP), exchange rate (EXCH), Real GDP growth rate (GDPR), Government expenditure (GEX), Inflation rate (INF), Money Supply (M2), Trade openness (OPN), Real Interest Rate (RIR) and unemployment (UNEM) were stationary at $I(1)$ and at constant, linear and trend level except for inflation (INF) that was stationary at constant with ADF. The pair-wise Granger Causality Test was used to investigate the relationship between exchange rate volatility and economic growth. Major findings from the study are outlined as follows:

- (i) There is no causal relationship between exchange rate volatility and economic growth in Nigeria.
- (ii) Exchange rate volatility recorded both positive and negative impact on economic growth although; the rate of negative impacts outweighs that of the positive impact.
- (iii) Trade balance has an insignificant positive effect on gross domestic product.

5.2 Conclusion

This study attempted to examine the impact of exchange rate volatility on economic growth in Nigeria. From 1970-2020. Useful policy options were suggested in line with our findings.

Several specifications and empirical literature suggested that exchange rate volatility would certainly affect economic growth either positively or negatively. Overall, the empirical results revealed a case of independence between exchange rate volatility and economic growth. It also discloses a significant relationship between exchange rate volatility and economic growth.

5.3 Recommendations

Arising from this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Reducing exchange rate volatility is quite crucial to mitigate its negative impact on money supply and output growth. Serious attention should be paid to factors that stimulate exchange rate fluctuations like high inflation and budget deficit. Thus, policymakers should consider adopting inflation targeting as a strategy in addition to the autonomy of the monetary policy.
2. Relevant authorities should try to avoid systematic currency devaluations in order to maintain exchange rate volatility at a rate that allows adjustment of the balance of payments.

3. Considering the current shortage of foreign exchange in Nigeria, the economy needs an effective exchange rate policy in order to overcome the unfavorable impact of declining foreign reserves. Therefore, an encouraging exchange rate should be offered for foreign transactions and transfers to attract flows of foreign capital such as FDI and migrants' remittances. In addition, diversification of the economy should be considered a top priority within the development agenda. In this respect, managing a competitive exchange rate would be a crucial tool to enhance productivity of the domestic sectors.

4. The government should encourage the export promotion strategies in order to maintain a surplus balance of trade and also conducive environment, adequate security as well as infrastructural facilities should be provided so that foreign investors will be attracted to invest in Nigeria.

5. More so, appropriate monetary and fiscal policies should be adopted to achieve a stable exchange rate regime to sustain economic growth and development in the country.

REFERENCES

- Adebisi, M.A. and Dauda, R.O.S (2009). Trade Liberalization Policy and Industrialization growth performance in Nigeria: An Error correction mechanism technique, being a paper presented at the 45th annual conference of the Nigerian Economic Society, 24th to 26th, Central Bank of Nigeria New Building Auditorium, Abuja.
- Adelowokan, O.A. Adesoye, A.B., and Balogun, O.D. (2015). Exchange rate volatility on investment and growth in Nigeria, an empirical analysis. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 15(10), 21-30.
- Adeniran, A., Yusuf, A. and Adeyemi O. (2014). Exchange Rate and Economic Growth. *Journal of Economic and Social Reserves*, (3), 1-4
- Aghion, P. F., P. Bacchetta, R. Ranciere, and K. Rogoff (2009). Exchange Rate Volatility and Productivity Growth: The Role of Financial Development. *Journal of Monetary Economics* 56 (4), 494-513.
- Aghion, Philip, Peter Howitt, and David Mayer-Foulkes (2006). The Effect of Financial Development on Convergence: Theory and Evidence. *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 120, 173-22.
- Alagidede, P., and Ibrahim, M. (2016). On the causes and effects of Exchange Rate Volatility on Economic Growth: *Evidence from Ghana (IGC Working Paper)*. London: International Growth Centre.

- Asher O. J. (2012). The impact of Exchange rate Fluctuation on Nigeria economic growth (198- 2010). *Unpublished B.Sc Thesis of Caritas University Emene, Enugu State, Nigeria.*
- Aliyu, S. R. U. (2011). Impact of Oil Price Shock and exchange rate Volatility on Economic Growth in Nigeria: An Empirical Investigation. *Research Journal of International Studies.*
- Alkhateeb, T. T.Y., Mahmood, H. and Sultan, Z. A. (2016) the relationship between exports and economic growth in Saudi Arabia. *Asian Social Science*, 12(4), 117-124.
- Alper, Ali Eren. 2017. Exchange Rate Volatility and Trade Flows. *Fiscaoeconomia* 1, 1-6.
- Akintola, M and Lawal, O. (2012). Exchange Rate Variability and Investment in Nigeria, Revisiting the Case for Flexible Exchange Rates: *Journal of economics Volume 5*
- Akinmulegun, S. O. and Falana, O. E. (2018) exchange rate fluctuation and industrial output growth in Nigeria, *International Journal of economics and Financial Research*, 4(5), 145-158.
- Akinsola, A. (2006). Foreign Exchange and interest rates Management-Issues and Challenges. *The Nigeria banker, January-July, 2002, p.23.*
- Akpan, E. O. and Atan, J. A. (2012) Effect of exchange rate movements on economic growth in Nigeria, *CBN Journal of Applied Statistics*, 2(2), 1-14.
- Akpan, P. L. (2008). Foreign exchange market and economic growth in an emerging petroleum based economy: Evidence from Nigeria (1970-2003). *African Economic and Business Review*, 6(2), 46-58.
- Anyanwu, F., Amalachukwu A., and Ngozi, O. (2017). Exchange rate policy and Nigeria's economic growth: A granger causality impact assessment. *International Journal of Applied Economics Finance and Accounting*, 1, 1-13.
- Apollos, E. A., Emmanuel, A. and Olusequn, D. J. (2015). Exchange rate volatility and economic growth in Nigeria (1986-2013). *Journal of Empirical Economics*, 4(2), 109-115. Retrieved from http://www.rassweb.org/admin/pages/Researchpapers/Paper%205_1497029926.pdf

- Arshad, M.U. and Usman M. (2017) impact of export on economic growth of Pakistan. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 8(16), 115-121
- Attah-Obeng, P., Enu, P., Osei-Gyimah, F., Opoku, C.D. (2013) An Econometric Analysis of the Relationship between GDP Growth Rate and Exchange rate in Ghana *Journal of economics and sustainable development*, 4(9), 1-8.
- Ayinde, T.O. (2014). The impact of exchange rate volatility on manufacturing performance: New evidence from Nigeria. *Fountain journal of management and social sciences*, 3(2), 83-92.
- Ayunku, P.E. and Etale, L.M. (2016) econometric analysis of external debt, exchange rate and economic growth in Nigeria, researchers *World-Journal of Arts, Science and Commerce*, 7(2), 83-89.
- Azeez, M., Kolapo, O. and Ajayi, A. (2012). The impact of exchange rate uncertainty on the Level of Investment. *The Economic Journal*, 109, 55-67.
- Azid, T., Jamil, M., and Kousar, A. (2005). Impact of exchange rate volatility on growth and economic performance: A case study of Pakistan, 1973-2003, *The Pakistan Development Review*, 44(4), 749-775.
- Azu, N.P. and Nasiri, A. (2015). Exchange rate fluctuation and sustainable economic growth in Nigeria: VAR approach, *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 6(13), 228-237
- Bagella, M., Becchetti, L. and Hasan, I. (2006). Real effective exchange rate volatility and growth: A framework to measure advantages of flexibility vs. costs of volatility. *Journal of Banking Finance*, 30, 1149-69.
- Bahmani-Oskooee, M. and Abera, G. (2018). Exchange-rate volatility and international trade performance: *Evidence from 12 Africa countries. Economic analysis and policy*, 1-22.
- Bailliu, J., Lafrance, R. and Perrault, J. F. (2001). Exchange Rate Regimes and Economic Growth in Emerging Markets. In *Revisiting the Case for Flexible Exchange rates*, 317-45. Proceedings of a conference held by the Bank of Canada, November 2000. Ottawa: Bank of Canada, 2002. Does exchange Rate Policy Matter for Growth? *Bank of Canada Working Paper No. 2002-17*.
- Bakari, S. and Mabrouki, M. (2016). The relationship among exports, imports and economic growth in Turkey, Munich Personal Re P Ec Archive, MPRA Paper No. 76044, 1-10.

- Barguelligil, A., Ben-Salha, O. and Zmami, M. (2018). Exchange Rate Volatility and Economic Growth. *Journal of Economic Integration (JEI)*. Volume 33 No 2.
- Barro, R. and David, G. (1983). Rules, Discretion and Reputation in a Model of Monetary Policy. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 12, 101-21.
- Basirat, M., A. and Jorjorzadeh, A. (2014). The effect of exchange rate fluctuations on economic growth considering the level of development of financial markets in selected developing countries. *Asian economic and Financial Review*, 4(4), 517-528.
- Berument, P. Ali, A. and Clement, A. (2012). Exchange Rate Volatility and Economic Growth in Turkey. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management United Kingdom Vol. V, Issue 7*.
- Bostan, Ionel, and Bogdan-Narcis Firtescu. 2019. Exchange Rate Effects on International Commercial Trade Competitiveness. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 11(19).
- Bleaney, M. and Greenaway, D. (2001). The impact of terms of trade and real exchange rate volatility on investment and growth in sub-Saharan Africa. *Journal of Development Economics*, 65, 491-500.
- Bosworth, B., Collins, S. and Yu-chin, C. (1995). Accounting for Differences in Economic Growth. *Unpublished manuscript. Brookings Institution, Washington DC*.
- Calvo, G., and Vegh, C.A., (1993). Exchange Rate Based Stabilization under imperfect credibility. In: Frisch, H., Worgotter, A. (Eds), *Open Economy Macroeconomics*. Macmillan, London, pp. 3-28.
- Campa, J. and Goldberg, L. S. (1995). Investment in manufacturing, exchange rates and external exposure. *Journal of International Economics*, 38, 297-320.
- Cushman, David O. 1986. Has exchange risk depressed international trade? The impact of third country exchange risk. *Journal of International; Money and Finance*, 5(3), 61-79.
- Dada, M. and Oyeranti, O. (2012). The impact of Exchange Rate Uncertainty on the Level of Investment. *The Economic Journal*, 109, 55-67.
- Dahiru A. B. and Asemota, J. O. (2013). Exchange-Rates Volatility in Nigeria: Application og GARCH Models with Exogenous Break. *CBN Journal of Applied Statistics*, Vol. 4 No. 1 (June, 2013) 89.

- Dal Bianco, S., and Nguyen, C. L. (2017). FDI inflows, price and exchange rate volatility: New empirical evidence from Latin America. *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 5(6).
- Danmola, R. A. (2013). The impact of exchange rate volatility on the macroeconomic variables in Nigeria. *European Scientific Journal*, 9(7), 152-165.
- Danladi, J. D. and Uba, U. P. (2016). Does the volatility of exchange rate affect the economic performance of countries in the West African Monetary Zone? A case of Nigeria and Ghana. *British Journal of Economics, Management and Trade*, 11(3), 1-10.
- David, U. and Ameh (2010). The effect of Exchange Rate fluctuations on Nigeria manufacturing Sector. *African Journal of Business Management*, 4(14), 2994-2998.
- Darby, J., Hallett, A. H., Ireland, J. and Piscitelli, L. (1999). The impact of exchange rate uncertainty on the level of investment. *The Economic Journal*, 109, 55-67.
- De Grauwe, P. (2007). *The economics of Monetary Union*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press, seventh edition.
- Devereux, M. and Engel, 2003, Monetary Policy in the Open Economy Revisited: Price Setting and Exchange-Rate Flexibility. *Review of Economic Studies*, 70(4), 765-783.
- Dickson, O. O. (2012). Exchange rate volatility and economic growth in Nigeria. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 3(3), 399-407.
- Dollar, David. 1992. Outward-oriented developing economies really do grow more rapidly: evidence from 95 LDCs, 1976-1985. *Economic Development and Cultural Change*, 40, 523-44.
- Dritsakis, N. and Stamatiou, P. (2016). Trade openness and economic growth: A panel co-integration and causality analysis of the newest EU countries. *Romanian Economic Journal*, 18(59), 45-60.
- Dubas, J. M., Lee, B. J. and Mark, N.C. (2005), Effective Exchange Rate Classifications and Growth". *NBER Working Paper No. 11272*.
- Edwards, S. and Savastano, M. A. (2000). Exchange Rate in Emerging Economies: What Do We Need to Know? In *Economic Policy Reform: The Second Stage*, ed. By Anne O. Krueger, pp. 453-510. Chicago: university of Chicago Press.

- Ehinomen, M. and Oladipo, O. (2014). The Impact of Exchange Rate Uncertainty on the Level of Investment. *The Economic Journal*, 109, 55-67.
- Eichengreen, Barry. 2008. The real exchange rate and economic growth. *Commission on Growth and Development Working Paper 2*, 1-48
- Etale, E. L. M. and Etale, L. M. (2016). The relationship between exports, foreign direct investment and economic growth in Malaysia, *International Journal of Business, Management and Economic Research*, 7(2), 572-578.
- European Commission (1990). *One Market, One Money: An Evaluation of the Potential Benefits and Costs of Forming an Economic and Monetary Union*. European Economy.
- Ewa, A. (2011) in Asher O. J. (2012). *The impact of exchange rate Fluctuation on the Nigerian Economic growth (1980-2010)*. Unpublished B.Sc thesis of Caritas University Emene, Enugu State, Nigeria.
- Frankel, J. and Andrew R. (2002). An estimate of the effect of common currencies on trade and income. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 117, 437-66.
- Frankel, J. (2003). *Experience of and Lessons from Exchange Rate Regimes in Emerging economies*, in monetary and Financial Cooperation in East Asia, Asian Development Bank, Macmillan, 2003.
- Gadanecz, A. and Mehrotra, L. (2013). Exchange Rate and Economic Growth. *Journal of Economic and Social Research*, (3), 1-4.
- Ganesh, A. I., Moses, L. and Musyoki, M. C. (2012). Exchange Rate Volatility and economic Growth in Kenya. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and management United Kingdom* Vol. V, Issue 6,
- Gbosi, A.N (2005). *Money, Monetary Policy and the Economy*. Port Harcourt: Sodek
- Hamdan, B. S. S. (2016). The effects of exports and imports on economic growth in the Arab countries; A panel data approach, *Journal of Economics Bibliography*, 3(1), 100-107.
- Holland, M., Vieira, F. V., da Silva, C. G. and Bottecchia, L. C. (2011). Growth and exchange rate volatility: a panel data analysis. *Applied Economics* 45: 3733-41.
- Hooper, P. and Kohlhagen, S. W. (1978). The effect of exchange rate uncertainty on the prices and volume of international trade. *Journal of International Economics* 8: 483-511.

- International Monetary Fund (1988). Exchange Rate Volatility and World Trade. *IMF Occasional Paper 28*.
- Ismaila, O. B. (2016). *Exchange Rate Uncertainty and Foreign Direct Investment in Nigeria*”, Trade Policy Research and Training Programme (TPRTP), University of Ibadan, Nigeria.
- Isola, I. A., Oluwafunke, A. L., Victor, A., and Asaleye, A. (2016). Exchange Rate Fluctuation and the Nigerian economic growth. *Euro Economic*, 35(2), 1-15.
- Iyeli, I. and Utting, C. (2017). Exchange Rate Volatility and economic Growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management United Kingdom* Vol. V, Issue 7.
- Jamil, M., Erich W. S. and Kunst, R. M. (2012). Exchange rate volatility and its impact on industrial production, before and after the introduction of common currency in Europe. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 2, 85-109.
- Janus, Thorsten, and Riera-Crichton, D. (2015). Real exchange Rate Volatility, Economic Growth and the Euro. *Journal of economic Integration*, 30, 148-71.
- Jhingan, M. L. (2011). *International Economics*. 6th Ed. India: Vrinda Publications Ltd.
- Jin, G., (2008). The Impact of Oil Price Shock and Exchange Rate Volatility on Economic Growth: *A comparative analysis for Russia, Japan, and China*. *Research Journal of International Studies*, 8, 98-111.
- Rashid, and Lin, L. (2018). The effect of exchange rate volatility on international trade and foreign direct investment (FDI) in developing countries along one belt and one road”, *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 6, 86.
- Lucas, R. (1988). On the mechanism of economic development. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 22(1), 3-42.
- Kandil M. (2004). Exchange Rate Fluctuations and Economic activity in Developing Countries: Theory and Evidence. *Journal of Economic Development*, 29(1).
- Kashif, A. Slade, M. E. and Blaze, K. (2010). Trends in natural-resource commodity price: an analysis of the time domain. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, 9, 122-137.

- Kyereme, S. (2004). Effects of exchange rate volatility and changes in macroeconomic fundamentals on economic growth in Ghana. *Institute of Statistical, Social and economic Research (ISSER)*.
- Matthews, T. (2010). *An essay on the principle of volatility*. St. Paul's Church.
- Mehta, S. (2015) The dynamics of relationship between exports, imports and economic growth in India, *International Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Sciences*, 3(7), 39-47.
- McKinnon, Ronald I. 1963. Optimum Currency Areas. *American Economic Review*. 53, 717-25.
- Mehdi, B., Arezoo, N., and Alireza, J. (2014). The effect of exchange rate fluctuations on economic growth considering the level of development of financial markets in selected developing countries. *Asian Economic and Financial Review*, 4(4), 517-528.
- Mordi, C. N. O. (2006). Challenges of Exchange Rate Volatility in Economic Management in Nigeria. *Central Bank of Nigeria Bullion*, 30(3).
- Mori, A., Asid, A., Lily, K. and Loganathan, O. (2012). Exchange Rate and Economic Growth. *Journal of Economic and Social Research*, 3, 1-4.
- Mukhtar, T. and Malik, S. J. (2010). Exchange rate volatility and export growth: evidence from selected South Asian countries. *SPOUDAI-Journal of Economics and Business*, 60(3-4), 58-68.
- Mundell, R. A. (1961). A Theory of Optimum Currency Areas. *American Economic Review*, 53, 657-65.
- Ndambendia, Houdou and Alhayky, Ahmed. (2011). Effective Real Exchange Rate Volatility and Economic Growth in Sub-Saharan Africa: Evidence from Panel Unit Root and Cointegration Tests. *The IUP Journal of Applied Finance*, 17(1), 85-94.
- Nzotta S. M. (2004). *Money, Banking and Finance: Theory and Practice*, Owerri: Hudson-Jude Nig. Publishers.
- Obadan, M. I. (2006). Overview of Exchange Rate Management in Nigeria from 1986 to Date” in the dynamics of Exchange Rate in Nigeria. *Central Bank of Nigeria Bulletin Vol 30, No. 3*.
- Obansa, S. A. J., Okoroafor, O. K. D., Aluko, O. O. and Millicent Eze (2013). Perceived relationship between exchange Rate, Interest Rate and Economic

- growth in Nigeria: 1970-2010. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 1(3), 116-124.
- Obstfeld, M. and Rogoff, K. (1998). Risk and exchange rates. *National Bureau of economic Research*.
- Odusola, A. F. and Akinlo, A. E. (2001). Output, inflation and exchange Rate in Developing Countries: An Application to Nigeria. *Journal of Development Economics* Vol 39, No.2.
- Ogun, O. (2006). Real exchange rate behavior and non-oil export growth in Nigeria. *African Journal of Economic Policy*, 11(1), June.
- Oyovw1, D. O. (2012) exchange rate volatility and economic growth in Nigeria, *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 3(3), 399-407.
- Okorontah, C. F. and Odoemena, I. U. (2016) Effect of exchange rate fluctuation on economic growth of Nigeria, *International Journal of Innovative Finance and Economic Research*, 4(2), 1-7.
- Pindyck, R. (2004) Volatility and Commodity Price Dynamics. *Journal of Futures Markets*, 24(11), 1029-1047.
- Pokhariyal, G. P., Pundo, M., and Musyoki, D. (2012). The impact of real Exchange rate volatility on the economic growth: Kenyan evidence. *Business and Economic Horizons*, 7, 59-75.
- Polodoo, V., Seetanah, B. and Padachi, K. (2011). Exchange rate volatility and macroeconomic performance in small island developing states, A paper presented at the WTO Chair Programme International Conference on International Trade and Investment (ICITI) held at Le Meridien Hotel, Mauritius, October 22, 1-33.
- RANO-Aliyu, S. U. (2009). Impact of oil price shock and exchange rate volatility on economic growth in Nigeria: An Empirical Investigation. *Research Journal of International Studies-Issue 1*, 21-34.
- Rogoffs, K. and Reinhart, C.M. (2004). The modern history of exchange rate arrangements: A reinterpretation. *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 119(1), 1-47.
- Romer, P. (1986a). Increasing returns and long-run growth. *Journal of Political Economy*, 94(5), 1002-1037.

- Salami O. A. (2005). The relevance of exchange rate on private foreign investment in Nigeria” between 1970 and 2001.
- Sakar, A. U. and Amor T. H. (2009). The effect of exchange rate disequilibrium and Financial Integration on Economic Growth”. *International Journal of Economics and finance, Vol. 1, No. 2.*
- Schnabl, G. (2008). Exchange rate volatility and growth in small open economies at the EMU periphery. *Economic Systems, 32, 70-91.*
- Shiller, I. and Radikoko, I. (2014). The study tests the validity of the weak-form EMH on the Canadian TSX equity market using seven companies. *Journal of Applied Economics. Vol. 4, 44-90.*
- Solow, R.M. and Swan, T. W. (1956) Economic growth and capital accumulation. *Economic Record, 32, 334-361.*
- Tarawalie, A. Robinson, P. and Allan, K. (2012). Exchange rate alignment and trade. *National Economic Review, 55-60.*
- Ubah, I. (2014). Impact of exchange rate volatility and economic growth. *Journal of Economic and Social Research, (3), 1-4.*
- Ubok-Udom, E. U (1999). Currency depreciation and domestic output growth in Nigeria: 1971-1995. *The Nigerian Journal, of economics and Social Studies, 41(1), pp. 31-44.*
- Ucan, O. (2016). The relationship between export and economic growth in Turkey, *European Scientific Journal, Special Edition (June), 61-70.*
- Ufoeze, L. O. Okuma, C. N., Nwakoby, C. and Alajekwu, U.B. (2018) effect of Foreign exchange rate in fluctuations on Nigerian economy, *Annals of Spiru Haret University economic Series, Issue 1, 105-122.*
- Umaru, H. Niyi, A. and Osagie, N. (2019). The effects of Exchange Rate Volatility on Economic Growth of West African English-Speaking Countries. *International Journal of Academic*
- Unugbro, A. O. (2007). The impact exchange rate fluctuation on capital inflow: the Nigerian experience. *The Nigeria Academic Forum, Vol. 13(2).*
- Vieira F. and MacDonald, R. (2016). A Panel Data Investigation of Real exchange Rate Misalignment and Growth, *42(3), 433-456.*